

INTERPRETATION OF SOME PROBLEMS ON UZBEK TRANSLATION OF ALL IDIOMS WITH THE EXAMPLE OF COLOURS (RANGLAR SO'ZI QATNASHGAN BARCHA IDIOMALARNING O'ZBEKCHA TARJIMASIDA UCHRAYDIGAN AYRIM MUAMMOLAR TALQINI VA IZOHI)

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Filologiya va tillarni o'qitish (ingliz tili) yo'nalishi 3-bosqich talabasi

Annotation: *Ushbu maqola shu qiyinchiliklarga yordam berish uchun ba'zi bir izlanishlar olib borgan holda, rangni ifodalagan so'zlari qatnashgan idiomalar ustida olib borilgan izlanishlar yoritilgan. Aniqliklar kiritish uchun misollar yordamida yoritilgan va izohlar bilan keltirib o'tilgan.*

Kalit so'zlari: *frazologik birliklarni tarjima qilish, hayvon nomlari ishtirok etgan frazeologik birliklar, uslubiy funktsiya, uslubiy rang berish, ekvivalent dastur.*

Idiomalarni so'zma-so'z tarjima qilish har bir tarjima uchun mos kelavermaydi. Ba'zi bir idiomalar borki ular bir vaqtning o'zida ham idioma ham bo'lishi mumkin, chunki kontekst uzatilmaydi; uni tushunish uchun asl tilni bilishimiz va ekvivalentni topish shu qadar rivojlanganki, ko'pincha ularning tarixi va asl ma'nosi yo'qoladi.

1. Feel blue- xafa bo'lmoq. Misollar yordamida tahlil qiladigan bo'lsak quyidagicha xulosaga kelish mumkin. Ex: I sometimes feel blue for unworthy things.

2. In the pink-sog'lom yaxshi bo'lmoq Ex: He has been in the pink since he started eating more fruits! Lekin noto'g'ri talqin etilsa pushti rangda bo'lmoq degan ma'noni anglatishi mumkin lekin ibora ma'nosida qo'llanilyapti.

3. Black mood- juda yomon kayfiyatda bo'lmoq, depressiyada bo'lish ma'noda! Lekin noto'g'ri yondashilganda esa qora kayfiyat bo'lmoq degan ma'noni anglatadi. Misollar bilan ko'radigan bo'lsak. The new staff came yesterday was a black mood at the beginning, but after a while he converted into a friendly one.

4. Golden opportunity-yaxshi imkoniyatda bo'lmoq! Lekin, ibora sifatida anglatilmasa oltin imkoniyat deb noto'g'ri tarjimani berar edi. Ex: In our country, the youngsters have got golden opportunities in every step.

5. Golden rule-qat'iy qoida Ex: Wearing special uniform is a golden rule for everyone in the group! Agar ibora ekanini payqalmaganida edi oltin qoida degan ma'noni anglatar edi.

6. Green fingers- yaxshi bog'bon bo'lmoq Ex: My pa was born with green fingers. He is great with plants, especially with flowers! Ammo, uni ibora ekanligini fahmlamay tarjima qilinganda, yashil barmoq deb tarjima berilardi va ma'no anglashilmas edi.

7. Paint the town red- o'yin kulgu qilmoq! Agar noto'g'ri yondashilsa shaharni qizilga bo'yamoq deb xato tarjimini berishi mumkin edi. Misollar bilan ko'radigan bo'lsak: ex: After the graduation of university, everyone painted the town red.

8. Shrinking violet- uyalmoq, o'z fikrini ochiq ayto'lmaslik! Binafsha rangni qisqartirmoq deb xato tarjima qilishdan ehtiyot bo'lish lozim. Ex: Jessica is no shrinking violet when expressing her views.

9. Black sheep- e'tiborsiz hurmatsiz a'zo Ex: Sometimes, George and Lucy play together happily, but now and then they fight like cat and dog. Their parents can't grasp their attitude towards each other and Lucy feels like a black sheep.

10. Born to the purple- ziyoli va boy oilada tug'ilgan bo'lmoq Ex: Rihanna was born to the purple her father was a director! Agar noto'g'ri yondashilganda va frazeologik birlik ma'nosiga e'tibor berilmay tarjima qilinganda u siyohda tug'ilmoq degan ma'noni anglatar edi. Shuning uchun uni asl ibora ma'nosini bilish va o'z o'rnida to'g'ri qo'llash kerak.

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